

MODERN INNOVATIVE METHODS OF TEACHING ENGLISH

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Annotation: The article is devoted to description of innovative methods to adults. Innovative methods and technologies of teaching today are gaining increasing recognition and new opportunities associated with the establishment of interpersonal interaction. The author pays attention to choices of methods which should vary with different purposes, ages groups, and stages of mental development.

Key words: ELF, methods, Trends, Cooperative learning, ELS, E-Learning, Innovative learning, learning process.

Essentially, the teaching process includes two main parts sending and receiving information. Eventually, a teacher tries his best to give knowledge as the way he understood it. The use of innovative methods in educational institutions has a powerful effect not only to improve education but also to empower learners. Trends have come in the field of education, and it affected the traditional system of education. Modern trends add vital role to the education sector in which the stress on quality over quantity. Such types of methods are called GTM (grammar- translation method) and Communicative method.

Traditional curriculum, class planning and old teaching routines help students to learn grammar and vocabulary for ages. One cannot deny that sometimes old methods of teaching makes learners get tired of memorising verbs, answering worksheets, and concentrating on repeating all the time. Though traditional methods such as audio - lingual and direct methods still offer useful results, yet they are clearly outdated in modern classroom. For sure social media and the internet as a whole have changed the way people learn languages in a positive way, it is imperative for modern language teachers to address the needs and interests of nowadays students. There are current and modern trends in teaching English that can help a lot of modern classes in learning the language in an EFL or ESL, easier and more effectively.

E - Learning: Web-based Learning: it is a recent way of learning from distance, in which this online education is based also on the four skills (listening, speaking, writing, and reading) but they can be on the web. Students prefer the e - learning and can communicate through using e-mails, blogs or chats because they are easy to learn, easy to use and well - designed. Such new a trend in teaching is good if it is just to support the main lecture but it cannot be a replace of the ordinary lectures. It is important to make sure that the e - learning is used correctly otherwise many problems will occur.

Creative thinking: Stimulate learners for creative thinking and think critically by including playful games and visual exercises, such methods really excites the learner's minds and stimulate their interest in learning. A teacher should always encourage new ideas of his students; it is considered one of the best ways to develop creative ideas and to encourage their freedom in exploring the new language.

Audio and Visual Materials: Teachers should not depend on the students' imagination, but he should include audio – visual Materials to his courses to ensure that the idea is understood better. Depending on audio – visual materials will help the development of the listening, reading and comprehension skills of students. There are also a number of ideas like inviting native guests; to listen to the right way of pronouncing words, presentations, data show, seminars or even using charts or poster presentation. The teacher should not let this visual or audio material to skip his domination role, for these materials are only aiding his job but are not as a substitute for his role. It is an undeniable fact that audio - visual was one of the operative ways in the past and in the present also; it enables students to practice what they have learned. It is really an effective way of teaching for learners can achieve communication by using gestures, eye contact and facial expression to convey meaning.

Brainstorming: Brainstorming should be included in class sessions. Make time to give a single important idea, a multiple brain focus to encourage each and everyone in the class to participate and to give voice to the student's thoughts without wondering if they might be wrong. Using a simple brainstorming session needs some ground rules before applying it in the class.

Outside Classroom: The environment really has a great effect on learners. Most of the best classes when they are outside the classroom; taking students outside the usual class refresh their ability and excitement in learning. Whatever is going to be given since is a change of routine is going to be remembered without much effort. This experience is considered as a field trip which helps to build experience for doing an assignment afterwards. The teacher should establish an objective for the event and connect it with the new environment, as the new location creates an inspiration, this will encourage the learner of the language to blend between the society and curriculum; students should make an assignment on the related topic. After the trip the learners can have a discussion in the class to connect what they have learned and highlighted the importance of such a trip.

Storyboard Teaching: Rudyard Kipling said, "If history were taught in the form of stories, it would never be forgotten." If a teacher connects each and every subject with a great storyboard, it helps students to learn step by step, for the effect of visualisation is highly effective in teaching. Such a way of teaching stimulate activity and even complex ideas will be easily dealt with. The Storyboard can be made either by the teacher or by the learner's imagination also.

7. Work Together As a Team: Teamwork is defined by Scarnati (2001) "as a cooperative process that allows ordinary people to achieve extraordinary results" (p. 5). As everyone knows, the result of every teamwork is always great and effective. Encouraging learners to do teamwork; one helps the other in their weak points to have a complete sharing project that each learner feels he is part of that afford. Maybe in a teamwork the teacher shares with his students the activity and all can be one great teamwork which is considered one of the best strategies in learning.

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Humour: It demands creativity and imagination to capture students' attention and interest in one's teaching. From students' point of view, a repetitious lecture would delay their interest to focus in the class. So adding humour in the class is so useful and motivates students' comprehension. There are benefits to include humour in the language classroom. Activities that can increase fun and learning by lowering students' nervousness are shared. It is important to teach students while playing and laughing, that avoids unease and keeps the thread of learning with no stress especially when there is a lot of work to do or when it is a very long session.

Stimulating Classroom Environment: A well - decorated classroom is a good environment for students to stimulate the learner's mind. It helps them to think better and encourage creative exploration. A positive environment for sure has a positive impact on its learners. Learners might bring the outside problems in the class like home problems or fear of tests or live pressure, which will lack their motivation and dulls the love of learning so using warm positive classroom really affects their learning ability and encourages them to ask questions and to be involved in the class lecture.

Engagement: It is important for students to be engaged with the real world, making learners involved in everyday life makes learning language easier and memorable. Instead of conventional teaching methods, students were taken to visit local businesses where they were able to witness how the knowledge that they were learning applied to the real world. Multiple days were set aside for this practice and all students were required to wear business suits in order to attend. The idea is to get students engaged and to connect their learning to the real world. Engaging learners with the real world makes learning more meaningful for students and they become more aware of the choices they make in society.

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